

RELIGION AS A DIPLOMATIC TOOL IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS: A MULTIFACETED INFLUENCE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Abstract

Religion, as conventionally attached to the private sphere, lately plays an instrumental role in international relations. This means that, while the world becomes more global, religion serves as an instrument for a country to extend its influence, build alliances, and contribute towards the cause of peace. This paper will look at how, within the cultural, spiritual, and moral restraints of statecraft, religion functions as a tool of diplomacy to strengthen international relations. It examines the dual roles that religion plays in diplomacy as a force of coherence and division. Thus, it can mediate solutions to conflict through encouraging interfaith dialogue that then aids peace-building processes. A notable example is the G20 Interfaith Forum, where leaders from G20 nations tackle global challenges like human rights and environmental protection. At times, strategic religious narratives might also trigger ideological divisions or conflicts. This paper captures some of these instances with clear case studies, more so by India, one of the proponents of religious diplomacy. The rise of the Hindu Right has seen religion being weaved into India's foreign policy as well, appending the objective of projection of a coherent national identity and upsurge in the soft power of the country on the global front. The potential for religion to serve as a diplomatic tool is huge, but when applied it should be handled with much caution in order not to exacerbate global tensions. To conclude, the strategic use of religion presents both opportunities and challenges to diplomacy, therefore shaping international relations crucially.

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Introduction

Religion is an integral part of culture and a prime factor in structuring societies and international relations. In today's world, often branded "clash of civilizations," religion intermingles with the surrounding cultural and political settings in very complex fashions. This has led to an increasing emphasis being laid on interrelations between religion and diplomacy, pointing the finger at the two, religious leaders and diplomats as collaborators in finding common agendas and forge engagement. Thus, religion in the 21st century can either facilitate a reconciliation of peace and stability or fuse as a wedge. Therefore, it is to be now used in peace making and diplomatic efforts.

In this context, an urgent question arises: To what extent may religion influence resolutions to diplomatic challenges? From a diplomatic standpoint, such inquiry naturally entails a specification of mechanisms through which religion may advance shared objectives and greater understanding. This question can only be settled if the diplomats grasp the possibilities of recognizing common goals and establishing a dialogue that joins the divided. In religious terms, the question will then be: In what manner can faith leaders be promoters of dialogue and agents of change making the world less violent and more harmonious? This will open the door for addressing the sets of doctrines and theological rationales that encourage discussions on peace and conflict solution.

The burgeoning "religionization" of politics and the politicization of religion mark a critical process by which religion influences diplomacy. Religion informs mankind as to how things should be, it stirs hearts to action, and it engenders ground-level disputes in international crises. Religious leaders wield immense influence within their communities, and their millennial message captures the hearts and minds of the general populace. Hence, consultation with religious figures should become a normal part of any diplomatic outreach. Forum-type activities proposing interfaith and intra-faith dialogues, grassroots social change, track-two diplomacy, and government-sponsored programs can strengthen their connections.

Some find religion as a peace making and some find religious dimension has to be conflict for instance Iraq , Kashmir and middle east countries these regions have the religious conflict, so whether religion is a root cause of conflict as it probably comes closest to being, in the Middle East where there are competing religious claim for the same piece of territory or a badge of identity and mobilising vehicle for nationalist or ethics, profession, it is never less central to strife that is taking place it also the case that most of these conflicts have an Islamic interface driven largely by the colonisation of globalisation with the tradition, values of an embedded in religion question is diplomacy can decrease the religious divide. Some countries are fighting on the name of religion, reclaim and some countries are trying to achieve peace through religion. So one of the most interesting challenges we face in global diplomacy. Today is a need to fully understand and engage the great impact that wide range of religious tradition have on foreign affair, religious actors, and institution playing an influential role in every region of the world and on nearly every issue for example in June Pope Francis historic encyclical “*laudato Si*” helped advocate for global measures to combat climate change. Religious advocacy groups have long raised awareness about famine and human rights violations abroad; Buddhist nuns in Nepal play a crucial role in natural disasters recovery efforts; and religious organisations have been essential in providing humanitarian support to Syrian refugees. So the question arrives here whether the How can faith leaders act as agents of engagement and change to make the world less violent and more harmonious? And Can diplomacy effectively mitigate religious divides?

Religion in Diplomacy as Tool

Religion is a multi-Valent force, not reducible to good religion and bad religion. Still, we must take seriously those when actor seeks to justify through religion rather than talking about the building a school, creating a community of providing the healthcare these act sometimes promote the destruction occasionally, for instance, 9/11 incident or for more example, in the central Africa, Republic Militia group, some of which are the Christian and Muslim are engaged in a bloody conflict, religious minorities in Burma, including the Rohingya a Muslim community are , subject to hate speech and controversial legislation that threatens religious freedom, although although religious leaders across world, Think there is much more that unite us and should unite us than divide us. Religion can be used as a diplomatic tool; it can function as a bridge between culture forums like G20, creating a mutual understanding with cultural exchange and also showing how religious narratives contribute to addressing global challenges such as human rights and environmental protection. not just g20 have a function of interfaith.

In 2013, John Kerry announced the creation of the office of religion and global affairs at the state department, which helps to implement President Obama’s US strategy on religious leader and faith community engagement. Its mission is clear to expand our understanding of religious dynamics and engagement with religious actors, the office lead was led by Susan Casey, a former professor of christian ethics at Wesley theological seminary, who is one of the country's leading thinkers on religion in public life. So the office mission was multifaceted First It provides high-level advice and policy matters as they lead to religion in many countries around the globe and comprehensive look at almost any policy area requires attention to religious dynamics. So the diplomat and minister under Obama regularly met with the religious leader and religious based organisations listening to their thoughts and situation in order to work with them on matters of significance to both sides. These religious actors and organisations are the key players in their countries holding influence at both local and national level. This office of religion and global affairs added many values on some of the most difficult international problems that the United States faces. One was the fight against climate change, a priority for the Obama administration and an issue that has long been important to the United States of America. It is also an area in which we have a strong partner in the religious community before Pope Francis’ issues his encyclical, organisation across the religious spectrum, raised the banner against global warming.

Way before the formation of the office of religion and global affairs The Bengali monk Swami Vivekananda of India (famously made this argument at a meeting of the Parliament of the world religions held during the Chicago’s World fair in 1893. India was unusual. Vivekananda insisted on being a nation that had sheltered the persecuted and the refuse genes of all religions and all nations of the Earth in his view, this was because Hinduism taught both tolerance and universal acceptance. For these reasons, he promised both western and Indian audiences that India would soon be recognised as a wish, God and world or universal guru, that would lead the world towards peace and mutual respect.

Diplomacy and Religion Perspective on Collaboration Diplomatic View

Many foreign policy makers of countries have sought to separate religion from world politics to liberate logic from beliefs that transcend logic. The Then president of the USA, Barack Obama Obama administration. There has been a movement to a more centric stance that acknowledges the possibilities of religious diplomatic cooperation because of realisation that religion is a large part of what motivates people and shapes their views, including the current prime minister of India, Narendra Modi. Think of the same. The more intersection of religion in diplomacy can motivate people and shape their views.

The approach that diplomats take toward cooperation and hence the agenda of their interactions with cherry-picking religious leaders tends to depend on the very circumstances in which they find themselves. Upon taking over from Henry Kissinger as Secretary of State, following the tenure he had as National Security Advisor under President Nixon, he addressed Foreign Service officers in the Apollo Court of the Department of State. Kissinger was firm upon stating that the starting point of any earnest analysis must be the objective circumstances relevant for that analysis through which an assessment should pinpoint possible opportunities as well as risks for U.S. policy.

Kissinger's state-centric focus during the Cold War was pragmatic, as foreign policy largely took shape from the thrust of geopolitics. But September 11, 2001 – and beyond it, from non-state terrorist groups professing to represent one, if not the one dominant, religious tradition – seriously shattered this given construct. These attacks demanded that the U.S. collective rethink its constructions on religiously embedded diplomacy.

Meanwhile, President George W. Bush recognized the political necessity of language; no longer would he refer in public speeches to a “crusade.” He held with leaders from different religious traditions a global day of prayer; he often invoked his own faith in his decision making process. It seems thus that a paradigmatic shift occurred from religion as a private issue toward religion as the new locus for international politics and diplomacy.

In other words diplomats and state representatives have increasingly come to recognize the value of religious engagement in international affairs. Yet diplomats are often wary of drawing attention to religious issues or engaging with religious leaders because of the potential to exacerbate, rather than bridge, differences of opinion.

A Religious View

Religion has played a profound and lasting role in human existence in shaping social values, ethical norms, and political frameworks. Diplomacy often poses a challenge and an opportunity together, sometimes in the role of a double-edged sword. In history, religious beliefs have played a key role in guiding the action of leaders, communities, and states, embedding morality into international relations. Interplay between faith and statecraft is becoming increasingly pertinent in this globalized, polarized world where the revivalism of religion challenges secularist assumptions of modernization. According to religion, diplomacy is a moral endeavour that aims to foster international collaboration, justice, and peace. Many religions promote global principles that are similar to the diplomatic principle of seeking justice, compassion, and reconciliation. The Bible's call to “bless the peacemakers” is one example of how Christianity promotes peacemaking. Similarly, the ideals of Buddhism's call for harmony and Islam's *sulah*, or peaceful settlement, offer direction in resolving international disputes. Therefore, these ideals emphasise the moral imperative of prioritising communication over aggression, resulting in a diplomatic approach that is not just geopolitically driven but also ethically motivated. Even in the latest interview of Indian external minister accepted that world best diplomats were Krishna and Hanuman, these two name are the most revered god mention hindu mythology texts. But religion may complicate diplomatic solutions, especially the process of negotiations if, instead of pursuing unity, they become a source of division. Rutledge notes that the absolute nature of some religious ideologies may become a hindrance to negotiations, since some prefer divine mandates and shun compromises. History, obvious examples being the Crusades, or more recent violence driven by religious extremism, shows how miscommunication through religion can thwart integrity in diplomacy. The resurgence of religious nationalism in countries like India and Israel makes international relations even more complicated by intertwining religious identity with political agendas, far too often towards the detriment of inclusiveness and peace.

What's for India? India's Religious Diplomacy

India's Religious Diplomacy has become one of the more visible aspects of the country's foreign policy, especially under the Narendra Modi government since 2014. The strategy uses India's extensive religious heritage to promote the country as a spiritual and cultural leader in the international arena. Yet, the philosophy underlying this diplomacy, its modalities, and its reception differ depending on the context and audience, raising critical discussions around its effectiveness and consequences.

India is the birthplace of four major religions: Buddhism realism, Jainism, Sikhism, and the major Centre for several others, including Christianity, Islam, Judaism, Zoroastrianism. The modern state of India, with its diversity, is often presented as a repository of spiritual knowledge that offers solutions to contemporary global challenges. This perspective has been prominently championed by the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) government, which portrays India as a *Vishwaguru* (world teacher), with Hinduism at the forefront of its diplomatic narrative. While earlier governments advocated a secular or broadly inclusive vision, Modi's administration has leaned towards promoting Hindu nationalist interpretations of India's cultural and spiritual contributions.

An overriding principle of this diplomacy is that it works to a dual audience: foreign nations and India's domestic and diaspora populations. For Western audiences, India presents a soft, inclusive Hinduism founded on practices like yoga and principles like environmentalism. Initiatives such as the International Day of Yoga often downplay Hindu nationalism in order to paint a universal picture. Conversely, for domestic and diaspora audiences, religious diplomacy tended to be more overtly Hindu nationalist. Modi's visits to temples abroad, and his rhetoric surrounding *Bharat Mata*, are aimed at upping Hindu pride and reaffirming Hindu nationalistic sentiments. From an institutional aspect, India's religious diplomacy receives support from both official and non-official actors. The Ministry of External Affairs, alongside bodies like the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR), plays the most important role, though limited resources are available. On the unofficial side, the diaspora organizations, the religious leaders, and the BJP-supported groups, such as the *Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh* (RSS) and the *Vishva Hindu Parishad* (VHP), amplify India's message abroad. They promote India's spiritual heritage and the unity of Hindus worldwide through cultural programs, educational initiatives, and interfaith dialogues. While this decentralized approach gives a lot of scope for flexibility, it brings challenges of how the narratives are maintained, especially at such times when certain sensitive issues can create controversies.

While some heads of state in Asia, particularly those from countries with shared Buddhist or Hindu legacies, have welcomed India's outreach, skepticism persists in the West regarding the essence of purposiveness of such outreach. Also, Western think tanks and governments have been questioning the government's stance over the marginalization of Indian Islam and Christianity. The net effect is one of knocking the established image of India on the pedestal within the international community, alongside demonstrating for vishwaguru. Religious diplomacy of the BJP works very well with its voting base, who feel Hindu identity is part of Indian nationalism. Among the diaspora, especially in the U.S. and U.K., the approach receives mixed reactions: while many support Modi's vision, some people don't like the mixing of Indian identity with Hindu nationalism. In addition, some of the promotion of Hindu nationalism abroad resulted in fragmentation within the diaspora communities and attracted scrutiny from foreign governments, concerned for its impact on social coherence.

Domestically, the BJP's religious diplomacy strategy finds resonance within its voter base, many of whom see Hindu identity as being intertwined with Indian nationalism. The reaction among diaspora communities, particularly in the U.S. and the U.K., however, is mixed. While large sections favor Modi's vision, some sections express unease over the merging of Indian and Hindu identity. Further, abroad, the promotion of Hindu nationalism has sometimes caused divisions within diaspora communities and drawn scrutiny from foreign governments, worried that it may take a toll on social harmony.

Conclusion

The world is moving towards a more religious spectrum and the world can be taught through the teachings of religion more easily. When S. Jaisankar mentioned Krishna and Hanuman. It was so praised and it was a trendy topic for that year. To conclude, India's religious diplomacy under the Modi government is a multi-pronged process that utilizes India's spiritual heritage both for international influence and domestic consolidation. While its methods of promoting yoga and reaching out to specific Asian partners have so far proven genuinely successful, the Hindu nationalist orientation may alienate non-Hindu minorities and foreign publics. For India to fulfill its goal of being a spiritual leader of the world, a more encompassing attitude that authentically embodies its pluralistic traditions may be essential. As the world dynamic shifting towards the religious spectrum, the world order is moving towards peace and unity with that also more conflict are rising.

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